

Gender influence and food safety: Another new challenge for public health in Cambodia and Pakistan

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Abstract: The purpose of this research is to explain the gender deference and food safety and challenges for the public of Cambodia and Pakistan. This task as based on a survey of the literature on foodborne disease (FBD) in low and middle-income countries (LMICs) and its impacts on consumers especially women and children. To identify and analyze deep-rooted understanding of “Foodborne Diseases” The references identified have first been screened to identify further toward the context of low and middle-income countries (LMICs). As the result of the study, low-income economies are identified as those with a GNI per capita, of \$1045 or less in 2014; middle-income economies are those with a GNI per capita of more than \$1045 but less than \$12,736. Perhaps as foods derived from animals, fish and aquatic animals (including meat, milk, eggs, offal, fish and crustaceans) and produce as fruits and vegetables sold fresh. Finally, the markets where traditional processing, products, and pricing predominate; where many actors do not comply with employment regulations and/or do not pay tax; and, which escape effective health and safety regulation.

Keywords: Gender, Food, health, safety, disease.

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Introduction

Food consumption in Cambodia and Pakistan is considered as important as the citizen mainly have their regular three times per day. Cambodia and Pakistan has gone through many social-political instabilities for decades especially from the 1970s in which the country has named itself below zero, where genocide and massive authoritarian politic had been implemented resulted in massacre due to inadequate food supplies, medical

care, strenuous labor exploitation, and certain term of abuses by the ruling authorities...etc. When it comes to hunger, everyone is counted. The WHO has developed the several indicators in coordinate with the global Sustainable Development Goals from 2015 to achieve by the end of 2030 under the umbrella of the United Nation in which goal number 2 out of 17 from the SDGs is related to having good health and well-being[1]. Foods play an important role to indicate and promote good health and well-being for every individual, but if people don't take close consideration over the nutrition fact from their consumed food, such consequences would have occurred. For example, cases from the low middle-income countries (LMICs) have shown that the way that their people are living and eating compound to several diseases and also caused by inadequate access to health services [2]. Foodborne disease is a major health concern in Cambodia; in 2017, there were 27 reported foodborne disease outbreaks. The Joint External Evaluation on International Health Regulation (2005) compliance found that Cambodia had a score of 2/5 on food safety, indicating the limited capacity in preventing and responding to outbreaks of foodborne diseases [3]. Evidence suggests many of these outbreaks stem from informal, "wet" markets Where many Cambodians and Pakistani buy their animal source food products, which are an important and healthy part of the local cuisine, particularly for children and women of reproductive age. Food safety is a top priority of Cambodian and Pakistani government, especially in informal markets where a majority of domestically produced foods are bought and sold [3]. FBD has been increasing in some developed countries and is likely to increase in LMICs as the result of massive increases in the consumption of risky foods (livestock and fish products and produce) and of lengthening and broadening value chains, bulking more food and increasing the distance between production and consumption. Rapid livestock and fish intensification may also lead to increased FBD as may the growing urban and peri-urban vegetable production relying on wastewater and untreated human and/or animal waste [2]. The economic effects of foodborne diseases and a lack of food safety are not explicitly documented in Cambodia, but evidence from other countries suggests a detrimental relationship [2]. Additionally, it is hypothesized that gender inequality surrounding nutrition contribute to greater economic and health inequities. This inequality also extends to economics; women tend to drop out of the complex chains that have more intense food safety regulations, preventing them from tapping into a profitable industry [4]. As discussed above, Cambodia has a high burden of foodborne illnesses and limited capacity to prevent these events [3]. Extensive research on food safety has not been conducted in Cambodia, but consumers and policymakers have concerns about food safety [5]. Animal-sourced foods seem to be the most hazardous, but these foods are an important part of the Cambodian diet, as well as an important part of the economy. Most animal source foods are obtained from local wet markets. However, previous evaluations of the effectiveness of government regulation in similar developing settings suggest that limited benefits. The International Livestock Research Institute has been involved in research and market-based interventions in Kenya, Nigeria, and India [4][6][7]. These interventions attempt to build capacity in the food chain system and use incentives, as well as encouraging corresponding policy changes. Before these interventions can be introduced, however, it is crucial to conduct formative research to understand the nutritional needs of these communities and how they interact with the wet markets, the intended target for intervention. Women are often very involved in the food chain system but do not always benefit from traditional interventions, due to their involvement in the informal systems. This formative review will focus on women with young children for a variety of reasons: in Nigeria, the only other country where gender differences were explicitly explored, researchers documented the different roles women have in the entire livestock to food chain system, as well as different interactions with food in the home; while men often had access to more and safer animal source food products, women and children had less access to these, despite high nutritional needs [4]. Therefore, this review and the eventual policy changes that may stem from it could benefit the health and economic security of women and children in Cambodia and Pakistan.

Research Methodology

The review was based on a survey of the literature on foodborne disease (FBD) in low and middle-income countries (LMICs) and its impacts on consumers especially women and children. To identify and analyze deep-rooted understanding of “Foodborne Diseases”, I have undertaken a research based on this keyword on few sources such as Google Scholar, Web of Science, Annual Reviews, International Journal of Environmental and Public Health and others. The references identified have first been screened to identify further toward the context of low and middle-income countries (LMICs). Learning from World Bank methodology, low-income economies are identified as those with a GNI per capita, of \$1045 or less in 2014; middle-income economies are those with a GNI per capita of more than \$1045 but less than \$12,736. Within the entire searching strand, the main sources have later been highlighted on the basis of the abstract, summary and/or the references part, which provided more than 20 references that urged to relate the most substantive contributions for understanding the respective FBD concept. FBD is defined as any disease that results from the ingestion of contaminated or naturally hazardous foods; animal source foods (ASF) are defined as foods derived from animals, fish and aquatic animals (including meat, milk, eggs, offal, fish and crustaceans) and produce as fruits and vegetables sold fresh. Finally, reviews have also detected specifically refer to “wet/informal market” definition, as a shared subject/purpose and facilitate communication of the framework, which refers to markets where traditional processing, products, and pricing predominate; where many actors do not comply with employment regulations and/or do not pay tax; and, which escape effective health and safety regulation.

Review Findings

1. Burden of Foodborne Diseases in the Developing/LMICs:

Global production and consumption of meat will continue to raise, from 233 million metric tons (Mt) in the year 2000 to 300 million Mt in 2020, as will that of milk, from 568 to 700 million Mt over the same period. Egg production will also increase further by 30% [8]. From this study, Dr. Delgado et al. concluded by giving advices for policy-makers to take a deep consideration over idea “Small-scale producers have to be linked vertically with processors and marketers of perishable products”. They claimed that the poor find it difficult to gain access to productive assets such as credit and refrigeration facilities, and to information such as knowledge about microbial infection prevention. The integration of small scale livestock producers and larger scale processors would combine the environmental and poverty alleviation benefits of small scale livestock production with the economies of scale and human health benefits that can be had from larger scale processing [8]. As a result, informed or even Educated men would gladly want to halt the livestock revolution. But the ongoing nutritional transformation as seen in developing countries driven by their income, population and urban growth leaves little room for policy makers to alter the widespread increase in demand for animal food products.

Likewise, the WHO reports indicate that illness due to contaminated food is the most widespread health problem in the world and an important cause of reduced socio-economic productivity. Food-borne infection is endemic in Nigeria. The 1997 Local Government Health System profile for Nigeria on reported leading causes of deaths in different zones showed that diarrheal cases accounted for 25% of mortality followed by malaria (21.0%) and accidents (9.8%) [9]. In Nigeria, as in most developing nations, there is no organized system for monitoring outbreaks of food-borne infections in humans [10]. Food borne diseases in Nigeria appear to occur predominantly as isolated sporadic cases rather than taking the form of outbreaks and many, if not most, cases of food-borne infections are unrecognized, un-investigated and undocumented. Moreover, many patients do not seek help from hospitals but may rather engage in self-medication or use medicinal herbs. It is, therefore, difficult to determine the actual incidence of food-borne infections. However, diarrhea is a good indicator of

food-borne disease and better data exist for the prevalence and impact of diarrhea in Nigeria. Worldwide, diarrhea is the second biggest killer of children under five years of age, accounting for 1.3 million deaths a year. Almost half of all the deaths of children under the age of five occurred in just five countries, of which Nigeria is one. The concentration of child deaths in a small set of countries is striking. This result is partly related to the large populations of children younger than five years in these countries, but also suggests that epidemiological, environmental and/or socio-economic conditions may underlay the high burden of diarrhea in Nigeria. The GBD study provides a comprehensive and comparable assessment of mortality and loss of health due to diseases, injuries and risk factors for all regions of the world [11]. The overall burden of disease is assessed using the DALY, a time Based measure that combines years of life lost due to premature mortality and years of life lost due to time lived in states of less than full health. The burden of diarrheal illness in Nigeria is 6,487,000 DALY. In 2012, the New York City Department of Health and Mental Hygiene began extracting information from Yelp—which publishes crowd-sourced reviews about local restaurants—and Twitter to detect real or potential foodborne illness outbreaks and also The Chicago Department of Public Health and its civic partners established “Foodborne Chicago,” a community approach to detecting disease outbreaks by monitoring Twitter feeds [12]. During March 2013–January 2014, Foodborne Chicago identified 2,241 “Food poisoning” tweets originating from Chicago and neighboring suburbs. From these, project staff members identified 270 tweets describing specific instances of persons with complaints of foodborne illness. Eight of the 270 tweets (3.0%) mentioned a visit to a doctor or an emergency department. A total of 193 complaints of food poisoning were submitted through the Foodborne Chicago web form [12]. The data continued to show more with the 133 Foodborne Chicago–prompted health inspections 27 (20.3%) identified at least one critical violation, compared with 16.4% of the 1,808 inspections not prompted by Foodborne Chicago.

Critical violations indicate an “immediate health hazard” resulting in a high risk for foodborne illness [12]. No health issue in China is more explosive than foodborne contamination and illness. Public confidence was badly shaken in the fall of 2008, when milk and infant formula adulterated with the industrial compound melamine killed six infants and sickened 294 000, and repeated scandals since then have continued to stir anxieties. “Food safety in China is far beyond a mere public health issue”, says Junshi Chen, chair of the National Expert Committee for Food Safety Risk Assessment [13]. As a consequence of these break-downs, disseminated infectious outbreaks in China are effectively invisible. The USA Estimated it had 3037 deaths due to foodborne illness in 2011, and just five infectious pathogens were responsible for 88% of deaths for which causes were identified (Table 2). China, by contrast, which has four times the population, reported only 137 deaths due to food poisoning in 2011 with just 14 attributed to microbial pathogens (Table 1). This miniscule number of victims is evidence not of a healthy country but of a weak surveillance system, says Jay Varma, who was chief of the US Center for Disease Control and Prevention’s (CDC) International Emerging Infections Program in China from 2007 to 2010: “The food safety problem in China is probably bigger than in western Europe or in the United States.

Finally, as regards food system regulation, the WHO and FAO had established a regional conference on Food Safety for Africa since 2005 in Zimbabwe which also could pilot the other LMICs. The meeting raised that stakeholders cite the following governance challenges: inadequate policy and legislation; multiple organizations with overlapping mandates; outdated, fragmented or missing legislation; inappropriate standards; lack of harmonization and alignment of standards; failure to cover the informal sector; limited civil society involvement; and, limited enforcement [14]. Significance and Caution of FBDs in LMICs There are few nationally representative surveys of food safety perceptions in LMICs, but smaller studies show high levels of concern over food safety. For example, results from seven countries found food safety was always a concern for consumers and often their single most important concern about food [5]. People’s actions (revealed behavior) confirm this: when pig diseases were initially reported

by the media in Vietnam, the majority of consumers either stopped eating pork, shifted to chicken or went to outlets perceived as safer [5]. Similarly, assessments conducted in the context of Rift Valley fever outbreaks in Kenya found that consumers asked to see butchers' certificates and demand for ruminant meat dropped as consumers switched to poultry [15]. Food safety has become an issue of enormous public concern in China [16][17]. One survey found Chinese people reported FBD was the second greatest risk they faced in daily life (after earthquakes), and 92% of respondents said they expected to soon become a victim of food poisoning [13]. Food safety can also affect trade. International trade studies have found evidence that the fixed costs of meeting standards tends to favor established exporters and leads to a greater reduction in developing-country exports relative to those in developed countries [18]. FBD can also lead to rejections and high economic costs. For example, the 1991 cholera outbreak in Peru, caused by consumption of water and seafood contaminated by *Vibrio cholera*, resulted in more than \$700 million in lost exports of fish and fish products [19]. More recently, in 2005, malachite green was found in Chinese eels resulting in export losses of at least \$860 million [20]. There has been little research on the intersection between gender and food safety in LMICs, but FBD can have important implications for women's resilience and vulnerability. Firstly, food safety has direct implications for women's health. Pregnant and lactating women are especially vulnerable to a range of FBD, including listeriosis and toxoplasmosis. (Interestingly, there are many taboos around consumption of food (especially nutritious food), for example, meat is the main target of proscriptions for pregnant women [21]. These taboos tend to protect from some FBD but have the disadvantage of worsening women's nutrition status.) Secondly, food safety has implications for women's livelihoods. Women have an important (even dominant) role in many traditional food value chains [22]. Concerns over food safety are often a driver in attempts to modernize and formalize food value chains. However, this may have the unintended consequence of excluding women. For example, although preparing poultry for consumption is traditionally a female role, the modern, private sector, poultry plants in South Africa employ mainly male workers; likewise, while women traditionally dominated milk marketing in West Africa, men predominate in the more recent, peri-urban dairying sector [22]. Lastly, women are risk managers in the realms of food consumption, preparation, processing, selling and, to a lesser extent, production, so gender analysis is important in designing interventions for improving food safety in informal markets. As concern with food safety increases, and standards ratchet upward, there is a risk that poor producers and value chain actors will be displaced from rapidly growing domestic markets. This has already occurred in export markets where smaller farmers tend to drop out, as they lack the human and financial capital needed to participate in highly demanding markets. For example, in the 2000s both Kenya and Uganda saw major declines (60% and 40% respectively) in small farmers participating in export of fruit and vegetables to Europe under Global Good Agricultural Practices (GAP). Food safety, therefore, has equity implications, and interventions to improve food safety should not be anti-poor [23].

FBD Impacts over Cambodian Women and Children: Like many Asian countries, Cambodia has a rich tradition of tasty and nutritious foods. Animal source foods (ASF) are an important part of the cuisine with pork, fish, and poultry products widely consumed. The great majority of livestock products are produced by smallholders, many of them women, and sold in traditional, wet markets, where women also predominate as retailers. Again, as common in Asia, recent years have seen growing concern over the issue of food safety. Welcome development is accompanied by urbanization, rapid increases in demand for livestock products and, as a consequence, rapid changes in supply chains, which become longer, more complex, and less transparent. Trust in food goes down; often with good reason as the food system develops in a way that provides little rewards for those with good practices, but high rewards for those who carry out bad and unsafe practices.

In Cambodia and Vietnam, most animal-source food products are produced by smallholders, many of them women, and sold in traditional open markets where women also predominate as retailers. However, value chain interventions have tended to favor men because they control the money from sales. Women who do much of the

work are poorly recognized and receive fewer benefits. Integrating gender in programs and projects aims to reduce gender gaps and enhance women’s participation in the economic development and women’s empowerment [24]. As a result from a study on the case of meat sellers in Nigeria over the influence of gender and group membership on food safety, men and women typically have very different roles in livestock production and processing with implications for food safety. Both men and women are more likely to rear smaller animals like goats and chickens, while men focus more upon larger animals like cattle and sheep. Women have some authority on decision-making for selling, slaughtering, consuming or control over income, especially over animals they rear. There are also notable differences between the north and south. A study in Ibadan from Nigeria and Nairobi, Kenya also looked at the role of men and women. Slaughtering cattle and dressing the carcass is considered an exclusively male occupation. Selling of meat and offal is done by both men and women, with men predominating in meat retail. Women are solely responsible for fetching of water. Women also have a predominant role in the cooking and selling of street food and a major role in preparation of food within the household. These different roles and responsibilities have implications for creation and management of risk [25] [26]. From the Safe Food Fair Food for Cambodia under the USAID fund over the food safety regarding a household survey on pork consumption, practices and healthcare-seeking behavior in Phnom Penh data in March to April 2018 has shown such remarkable unreported fact in this developing nation’s livelihood reality [27]. With a total of 200 participants with an average age of 42.1 years old ranging from 18-75, there is a mass contribution from female (91.1%) (Table 3) side since their responsibility and/or task in this traditional state involved with housekeeping simply called housewives and wherein women may be discouraged from access to upper secondary and higher education, participation in decision making within and beyond the household level, have limited security even within the household etc. ...[28].

Table 3: Percentage of Gender Comparison from household survey on Pork Consumption Practices and Healthcare-Seeking Behavior in Phnom Penh Source: SFFF Cambodia, PI: Calgary NGOs.

The survey continued to tell about the concern of the characteristic of pork in which cleanliness is the most significant characteristics among all others with almost 98% (Table 4) [27]. Food safety is really a concern for almost all of the participants but unfortunately their reference is still driven by convenience/accessibility, not by food safety concerns.

Buyer characteristics, %

Characteristic	Level of importance		
	Very important - important	Not important	Don't know
Price	73.3	26.2	0.5
Trust in seller	73.3	26.7	0
Personal relation	66.8	33.2	0
Regular availability	61.4	38.1	0.5
Accessibility	82.2	17.3	0.5
Packaging	94.6	5.4	0
Cleanliness	97.5	2.5	0
Safety	83.6	5	11.4
Nutritional value	86.1	3	10.9

Furthermore, it is still a challenge for this citizen to fully aware of the issue of FBDs from their daily consumption due to the fact that there is ironically a limited knowledge of food safety and foodborne health risks to Cambodian especially women as the housekeeper/cooks inside their individual households. For instance over this case, women have been treated negatively in which there are many myths and misunderstandings which limit the nutrition of pregnant women and breast-feeding mothers which is a detriment to not only the woman’s health but that the unborn or new born child. Pregnant women are sometimes wrongly advised to eat less (since it will make delivery, of the smaller fetus, easier), to avoid white rice porridge and banana flower, but should (wrongly) drink traditional alcohol medicine. Similarly, breastfeeding women are wrongly told avoid vegetables (wrongly believing that They will cause abdominal pain, vein swelling, cramping and heartburn), some fruits such as jack-fruit, pineapple and bananas as well as some types of meat and fish [28]. Not only the mother but also their children are at risk in which the policy for early childcare policy has been enforced rather theoretically leaving the reality behind which women and children are being condemned. The emerging challenges for the Royal Government of Cambodia (RGC) form the Education for All (EFA) policies including goal number one related to “Childhood Care and Education” are currently struggling to improve quality of early childhood education, care and nutrition program and increase usage of health services for children aged 1 – 6 years. [29][30].

Conclusion

There is reasonable evidence that LMICs bear the brunt of FBD; that developing country consumers are concerned about FBD; that most of the known burden of FBD disease comes from biological hazards; and, that most FBD is the result of consumption of fresh, perishable foods sold in informal markets. While we don’t have good data on the burden of FBD in LMICs, microbial pathogens may cause a burden of 18 million DALYs a year, foodborne parasites at least the same, and aflatoxins 1–2 million DALYs. The full burden of chemical hazards is not known. Food safety has been neglected in LMICs such as Cambodia, and Pakistan where most efforts to reduce diarrhea have focused on water, sanitation and hygiene. Likewise, it is clear that the prevention of diarrhea in infants and children requires a multidisciplinary approach, including the promotion and protection of breast-feeding as well as the safe preparation and handling of weaning food. In view of this, the education of local mothers on food safety principles is one of the most important interventions in promoting the health and nutritional status of infants and children. However, these interventions and improvements still leave a large proportion of diarrheal disease unmanaged and evidence is growing that FBD may be an important contributor to health burdens. Moreover, as good progress continues to be made in attaining clean water and sanitation goals, FBD may be-

come more salient. FBD has been increasing in many other developed countries and is likely to increase in Cambodia as the result of massive increases in the consumption of risky foods (livestock and fish products and produce) and of lengthening and broadening value chains, bulking more food and increasing the distance between production and consumption. Rapid livestock and fish intensification may also lead to increased FBD as may the growing urban and peri-urban vegetable production relying on wastewater and untreated human and/or animal waste.

There is limited evidence on effective, sustainable and scalable food safety interventions but some promising approaches. Building on the existing food system may be more successful than attempting to impose completely new systems. Given the importance of FBD, better impact assessment of interventions to improve food safety is a priority. There are opportunities to improve food safety through technologies, value chain innovations and restructuring of food safety governance, but the feasibility and effectiveness of these is not Well understood. However, the widespread concern over food safety in LMICs and the growing evidence of the associated health burden and economic costs from different cases in Cambodia, and Pakistan make it likely that this area will receive greater attention in future. Therefore, future research could be developed following such gaps which this review has pointed out some regarding providing recommendations for enhanced engagement and benefit sharing for men and women in ASF value chains through improving understanding of gender aspects and the gender appropriateness of interventions and also by integrating nutrition and food safety, as well as building capacity in understanding food safety risk, its management, and effective communication among stakeholders including the royal government, private sector, academia, donors, and media.

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